

Attract attention on your resource

Constantly working on the visibility of your resource is essential to position it as a reference in your domain.

Get listed

Getting your resource added to **prestigious lists** curated by **international organizations** will increase **visibility** and **recognition**.

Consider applying for:

- ❖ **SIB/ELIXIR-CH Service Delivery Plan (SDP)** identifies resources that provide long-term, sustainable, and high-quality services to the bioinformatics community.
- ❖ **SIB Resources** form a portfolio of carefully selected databases and software tools from among SIB groups identified by SIB's Scientific Advisory Board.
- ❖ **ELIXIR [Core Data Resources \(CDR\)](#) and [Deposition Databases \(EDD\)](#)** are a set of European data resources of fundamental importance to the wider life-science community and the long term preservation of biological data.
- ❖ **ELIXIR [Recommended Interoperability Resources \(RIRs\)](#)** facilitate the FAIR-supporting activities in scientific research.
- ❖ **[Global Core Biodata Resources \(GCBRs\)](#)** are of fundamental importance to the global life sciences community and the long-term preservation of biological data.

Contact the Biodata Resources team for more information.

Be visible at congresses and meetings

- ❖ Plan the number of congresses and meetings to attend with your teammates each year.
- ❖ Be easily **recognizable**, wear branded pins or T-shirts.
- ❖ Bring goodies (like stickers or else) to engage attendees.
- ❖ Use the **SIB booth**, if available, for networking.
- ❖ Contact the **Communications team** to **promote** your attendance on **social media**.

Use the opportunities provided by your SIB membership

Participate in the initiatives to catch the limelight, such as:

- ❖ **SIB Remarkable Outputs** Annual competition.
- ❖ **Bioinformatics Awards** Bi-annual competition (organized by SIB).
- ❖ **SIB days / [BC]²** participation in the scientific committee, talks & posters, social activities...
- ❖ **Focus groups** Participate or launch your own topic (see [existing topics](#)) & look for partnerships.

Getting featured thanks to these initiatives guarantees that your resource will also get visibility in dedicated **SIB social media** campaigns and **website**.

Propose and prepare training kits to reach students

Getting students hooked on your resource early helps to ensure they will use it **throughout their career**.

Reach out to university biology and/or bioinformatics departments to propose a training kit or even an intervention in courses to show **how to use the resource** and for which purposes.

Share impact stories on your website and elsewhere

Impact stories highlight how your resource drives **innovation** in life sciences, helping **potential users** see its practical applications and giving **decision-makers** a clear sense of its importance.

SIB features these stories on its [website](#), **social media**, and different **reports**. Do not hesitate to contact the Communications team for assistance.

Ask your users for testimonials or referrals

- ❖ Ask your users for **testimonials** and **referrals** on their social media or website.
- ❖ Request **quotes** from Scientific Advisory Board members to **share** on your platforms or through SIB communications.

Get involved in societies

Such as the [International Society for Computational Biology \(ISCB\)](#), [Life Science Switzerland \(LS²\)](#) or any other one related to your user base.

Develop your social media presence

Regular updates on relevant social channels **build trust** and strengthen **relationships with users**. SIB currently focuses on **LinkedIn** and **Mastodon** for institutional communications. Contact the **Communications team** for platform expertise and a **tailored strategy**.

- ❖ **LinkedIn showcase page:** the communications team encourages the creation of LinkedIn Showcase pages to publish updates independently but with full support from the communications team. The first example is the [Cellosaurus showcase page](#).

Keep the Communication team in the loop

When your team is represented at a conference, panel, or in the media, inform the Communications team in advance.

They will help you promote it in the most efficient way.

Your contacts:

[Communications team](#)
[Biodata Resources team](#)

Swiss Institute of
Bioinformatics